

Tutorial

TCAD simulation of Fe-SBFET

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Summary

This tutorial describes the TCAD workflow developed for the simulation of the Ferroelectric Schottky Barrier Field Effect Transistor (Fe-SBFET). The document contains a description of the approaches and models used in the 2D and 3D TCAD setups, adapted to different device design options. The models have been calibrated to experimental measurements of structures fabricated by collaborators at the Institute of Solid State Electronics in TU Wien. Simulation results and comparison between different models and simulation approaches are presented. TCAD simulations have been performed with Synopsys Sentaurus TCAD¹.

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¹ <https://www.synopsys.com/manufacturing/tcad/device-simulation.html>

1. Introduction

The Fe-SBFET is based on the ferroelectric polarization-induced modulation of the Schottky barrier at the junction between source and drain metal and the semiconductor region. In particular, the tunnelling at the Schottky barrier is modulated by the polarization-induced band bending in the semiconductor layer. This device can be fabricated using two different design options, shown in Fig. 1. In a first option (Fig. 1.a), the ferroelectric layer is present only on top of the Schottky junctions at source and drain. In this case, the ferroelectric polarization can only affect the Schottky barriers, while it does not modulate the carrier concentration in the middle of the channel. The program gates placed on top of the ferroelectric layers are only used to set the polarization state and an additional gate electrode is needed to turn on the FET and read the drain current, which is influenced by the ferroelectric polarization. This gate can be an additional front gate or a back gate, as depicted in Fig. 1.a. Here we will consider a back gate,

Figure 1. Two different design options for the Fe-SBFET: a) the ferroelectric layer lies only on top of the source and drain Schottky junctions; b) the ferroelectric layer extends also on top of the semiconductor channel region.

as this structure has an easier fabrication process and for which experimental realization are more easily found in literature².

The second option (Fig. 1.b) employs a ferroelectric layer on top of both the source/drain Schottky junctions and the FET channel. This device is similar to a conventional FeFET, but with Schottky contacts placed below the ferroelectric layer such that they can be modulated. Fabricated Fe-SBFETs using this design have been also reported in literature³. In this device we have both the polarization-induced Schottky barrier modulation and the polarization-induced modulation of carrier concentration in the channel. Even though a back gate can be used to perform specific synaptic functionalities, for a simple memristor only a single gate is needed in this case for both setting the polarization and reading the drain current.

Different TCAD simulation setups have been developed to simulate these two device options in 2D and 3D. This tutorial is more focused on the first design in Fig. 1.a.

2. TCAD simulation flow: structures and models for device simulations

Before describing the TCAD simulation workflows of the full devices including both the ferroelectric layer and the Schottky junctions, individual modeling of the two sub-blocks is detailed. The tutorial will first address the modeling and simulation of polarization switching in ferroelectric layers, then it will address Schottky junctions modeling and finally it will present simulations of the full devices.

a. Simulation of ferroelectric layer

Within the Sentaurus TCAD simulator, two different models are available to simulate the behaviour of the ferroelectric materials: one is based on the Preisach model and one is based on the Ginzburg–Landau–Khalatnikov equation.

A Preisach-based model is a phenomenological model that describes a macroscopic hysteretic system composed by a superposition of simple hysteresis units, where each unit has a rectangular hysteresis loop⁴. Fig. I shows a ferroelectric thin film capacitor represented as a system of parallelly connected, non-interacting units with rectangular hysteresis: the switching charge θ , and the coercive voltages α and β , for each unit can be different, resulting in a smooth total hysteresis loop (Fig. I.c). In Preisach-based models for ferroelectric hysteresis, the polarization (P) versus electric field (F) relation is modelled using a hyperbolic tangent function because it is a simple form, it has the correct physical properties, and provides a

² F. Xi et al., Adv. Electron. Mater. 2023, 9, 2201155, DOI: 10.1002/aelm.202201155; D. Nazzari D, et al., ACS Appl Mater Interfaces. 2025 Feb 19;17(7):10784-10791, doi: 10.1021/acscami.4c16400

³ F. Xi et al., ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces, 13, 27, p. 32005, 2021; F. Xi et al., IEEE JEDS, vol. 10, pp. 569, 2022; V. Sessi et al., in Proc IEEE-NANO 2018, p.1; V. Sessi, et al., Adv. Electron. Mater., 6, p. 1901244, 2020.

Figure I – (a) Ferroelectric thin film capacitor represented as an hysteretic system composed by a superposition of hysteresis units with rectangular hysteresis (b). α , β and θ for each unit can be different resulting in smooth hysteresis loop (c).

reasonably good agreement with experiments for most ferroelectric thin film capacitors⁴. The equation used by Sentaurus Device is the following⁵:

$$P = c \cdot P_s \cdot \tanh(w \cdot (F \pm F_c)) + P_{off}$$

where

$$w = \frac{1}{2F_c} \ln \frac{P_s + P_r}{P_s - P_r}$$

and P_s is the saturation polarization, P_r is the remanent polarization (see Fig. 2), F_c is the coercive field, P_{off} and c are used to account for the polarization history of the material. The model features also minor loop nesting. Sentaurus Device memorizes turning points, i.e. points in the P – F diagram where the sweep direction of the electric field F changes from increasing to decreasing or viceversa, as they are encountered during a simulation. The memory always contains the points defining the two curves of the saturation loop (with $c = 1$ and $P_{off} = 0$), i.e. (∞, P_s) and $(-\infty, -P_s)$. All other pairs of turning points result in $c < 1$ and $P_{off} \neq 0$ and define a

Figure II – a) Polarization and electric field in a ferroelectric capacitor. b) Polarization – electric field curve simulated by Sentaurus TCAD using the Preisach-based model. The points on the polarization curve are reached in the sequence a, b, c, d, e, f, g, f, h, i, k, i, e, c. The diagram also illustrates the feature of minor loop

⁴ B. Jiang *et al.*, Computationally Efficient Ferroelectric Capacitor Model for Circuit Simulation, 1997 Symposium on VLSI Technology Digest of Technical Papers, p.141

⁵ Sentaurus Device of Synopsys TCAD, User Guide, V-2023.12

pair of curves forming minor loops (see Fig. 2.b). Sentaurus Device also features transient simulations by employing auxiliary polarization and auxiliary electric field². The parameters of the Preisach-based model, i.e. F_c , P_s and P_r have been calibrated to describe the experimental polarization versus electric field curve of the HZO capacitors (simple HZO layer between two metal electrodes) fabricated and measured in TUWien. The results are shown in Fig. III. It reports experimental data about the charge on the capacitor plate (Q), which is the quantity actually measured and the polarization, which was computed according to:

$$Q = P + \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_{FE} F$$

where ε_{FE} is the dielectric background constant of the ferroelectric material. For HZO, it is in between 25 and 35⁶; within this range, the parameter is often used as a fitting parameter. For the curve in Fig. 3, a value of 35 was selected because subtracting $\varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_{FE} F$ to Q a flat polarization curve is found for very high (absolute) values of electric field: this is consistent with the Preisach-based model. In simulations, the charge and polarization quantities can be independently printed out and extracted. The simulations of the HZO capacitor were performed in Sentaurus Device using the parameters $F_c = 1$ MV/cm, $P_s = 23$ $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and $P_r = 21.5$ $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$. The model provides a very good agreement with experimental results.

Figure III – Measured (symbols) and simulated (solid lines) charge (Q) and polarization (P) of a parallel plate HZO capacitor, showing very good agreement between experiments and the Preisach-based model.

The model employing the Ginzburg–Landau–Khalatnikov equation^{7,8} is based on the Landau theory for ferroelectric materials. In the Landau theory, the ferroelectric material is described

⁶ J. Muller, *et al.*, "Ferroelectric Hafnium Oxide Based Materials and Devices: Assessment of Current Status and Future Prospects", ECS J. Solid State Sci. Technol., vol. 4, no. 30, 2015.

⁷ M. E. Lines, *et al.*, "Principles and Applications of Ferroelectric and Related Materials", Clarendon Press, Oxford 1977

⁸ P. Lenarczyk, *et al.*, "Physical Modeling of Ferroelectric Field-Effect Transistors in the Negative Capacitance Regime", International Conference on Simulation of Semiconductor Processes and Devices 2016

through a proper thermodynamic free energy⁹. In Sentaurus TCAD, the free energy of a ferroelectric material occupying a region is written as¹⁰:

$$G = \int_{\Omega} \left(\alpha_i P_i^2 + \beta_i P_i^4 + \gamma_i P_i^6 + g_{ij} \left(\frac{\partial P_i}{\partial x_j} \right)^2 - E_i P_i + \frac{\varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r}{2} E_i E_i \right) d\Omega$$

The first three terms represent the Landau free energy functional (energy stored due to polarization) and the fourth term accounts for the energy caused by nonuniform polarization and represents the energetic cost of forming domain walls. In the Ginzburg–Landau–Khalatnikov framework, the governing equation of polarization evolution can be obtained as a gradient flow associated with the free energy functional¹⁰:

$$\rho \frac{dP_i}{dt} + \nabla_{P_i} G = 0$$

From the two equations above, the following is found:

$$\rho \frac{dP_i}{dt} + 2\alpha_i P_i + 4\beta_i P_i^3 + 6\gamma_i P_i^5 - 2g_{ij} \frac{\partial^2 P_i}{\partial x_j^2} - E_i = 0$$

where P_i and E_i denote the Cartesian components ($i, j = x, y, z$) of the polarization vector and the electric field vector, respectively. Following a common practice, we assume that HZO shows a polarization aligned along the applied electric field direction (see Fig. II.a). Thus, we use only one Cartesian component.

The Landau coefficients α , β , γ have been calibrated to fit the polarization versus electric field measurements of the HZO capacitor already shown above. The results of TCAD simulations, compared to experimental data are shown in Fig. IV. It has to be noted that in this case the dielectric background constant of the ferroelectric material used to compute the polarization from the measured charge data was 26. This value, used also in the corresponding simulations, was chosen so as to obtain a small slope in the polarization curve at high (absolute) electric field: in fact, by using the Ginzburg–Landau–Khalatnikov equation, the polarization is not as completely flat for field values larger than the coercive field, but it features a small increase with electric field. The simulated results have been obtained using the following parameters: $\alpha = -3.22 \cdot 10^{10}$ cm/F, $\beta = -2.34 \cdot 10^{19}$ cm⁵/(FC²), $\gamma = 8.39 \cdot 10^{28}$ cm³/(FC⁴). The simulated curves present a sharp polarization switching when the electric field reaches the coercive field. This is due to the fact that the ferroelectric layer was described using a single region with constant α , β , γ parameters, leading to the same coercive field for the entire ferroelectric layer. It has to be noted that in this picture the ferroelectric layer can still divide in different ferroelectric domains, for example when the ferroelectric layer sits on a dielectric layer and an inhomogeneous electric field triggers the formation of ferroelectric domains. However, this picture featuring a single coercive field cannot accurately reproduce the fairly gradual switching seen in experiments, which is given by the fact that HfO₂-based ferroelectric materials are polycrystalline, where each grain may have a somewhat different polarization reversal, namely different coercive fields and remanent polarization. TEM and SEM images

⁹ K. Majumdar, *et al.*, “Revisiting the Theory of Ferroelectric Negative Capacitance,” IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices, vol. 63, no. 5, pp. 2043–2049, May 2016. doi: 10.1109/TED. 2016.2544813

¹⁰ Sentaurus Device of Synopsys TCAD, User Guide, V-2023.12

Figure IV - Measured (symbols) and simulated (solid lines) charge (Q) and polarization (P) of a parallel plate HZO capacitor. Simulations are done employing the Ginzburg–Landau–Khalatnikov equation (and one single region with uniform α , β , γ parameters).

evidence grains that have a fairly uniform polarization, meaning that each polycrystalline grain corresponds to a ferroelectric domain^{11,12,13}. It is also assumed that the polarization in one grain does not influence the polarization in the adjacent grains, so that the different grains are coupled only by the electrostatics. It is thus possible to model a ferroelectric layer featuring multidomains by dividing the region in ferroelectric boxes connected by non-ferroelectric spacers¹⁴, as illustrated in Fig. V. Each box represents a ferroelectric domain, in which the polarization is constant: this is obtained by penalizing the formation of domain walls inside each box, i.e. by setting the parameter g_{ij} to a high value. Similarly to the Preisach theory, each domain can be assigned a different coercive field (by changing the α , β , γ parameters of the domain) in order to obtain a smooth transition between the two polarization states in the polarization versus electric field curve. The results of the simulations done using such a strategy are reported in Fig. VI. The α , β , γ parameters have been obtained to have a Gaussian distribution of coercive fields with a mean of 1 MV/cm and a standard deviation of 0.4 MV/cm. The simulated polarization versus electric field shows a very good agreement with the experimental data.

¹¹ H. Mulaosmanovic *et al.*, "Switching Kinetics in Nanoscale Hafnium Oxide Based Ferroelectric Field-Effect Transistors", ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces, 9, 3792-3798, 2017

¹² M. H. Park *et al.*, "Surface and grain boundary energy as the key enabler of ferroelectricity in nanoscale hafnia-zirconia: a comparison of model and experiment", Nanoscale, 9, 9973, 2017

¹³ F. P. G. Fengler *et al.*, "Domain Pinning: Comparison of Hafnia and PZT Based Ferroelectrics", Adv. Electron. Mater., 3, 1600505, 2017

¹⁴ D. Lizzit, *et al.*, "Multi-level Operation of FeFETs Memristors: the Crucial Role of Three Dimensional Effects" ESSDERC 2022 - IEEE European Solid-State Device Research Conference (ESSDERC)

Figure V – Ferroelectric layer divided in ferroelectric boxes connected by non-ferroelectric spacers: such structure is constructed and simulated in TCAD to describe the polycrystalline nature of HfO₂-based ferroelectric material and to represent the smooth transition in the polarization – electric field curve measured experimentally.

Figure VI - Measured (symbols) and simulated (solid lines) charge (Q) and polarization (P) of a parallel plate HZO capacitor. Simulations are done employing the Ginzburg–Landau–Khalatnikov equation and dividing the ferroelectric layer in multidomains with different α , β , γ parameters.

b. Simulation of Schottky junctions

In Sentaurus Device it is possible to simulate a Schottky barrier by imposing a specific boundary condition at a metal/semiconductor interface or at an electrode contacting a

semiconductor region (which acts as an electrical boundary condition). The boundary conditions imposed by the simulator to model a Schottky interface/contact are the following¹⁵:

$$\varphi = V_{\text{applied}} - \phi_B + \frac{kT}{q} \ln\left(\frac{N_C}{n_i}\right)$$

$$\vec{J}_n \cdot \hat{n} = qv_n(n - n_0^B) \quad \vec{J}_p \cdot \hat{n} = qv_p(p - p_0^B)$$

where

- ϕ_B is the Schottky barrier height, which is defined as the Schottky barrier for electrons, i.e. the difference between the metal contact work function and the electron affinity of the semiconductor: $\phi_B = \phi_{Bn} = q\phi_M - q\chi$. The Schottky barrier for holes is the difference between the semiconductor bandgap and the Schottky barrier for electrons: $\phi_{Bp} = E_g - \phi_{Bn}$
- v_n and v_p are the thermionic emission velocities for electrons and holes, respectively
- n_0^B and p_0^B are the equilibrium densities:
 - o $n_0^B = N_C \exp\left(\frac{-q\phi_B}{kT}\right)$
 - o $p_0^B = N_V \exp\left(\frac{-E_g + q\phi_B}{kT}\right)$

It can be shown that the latter equations for the current densities are equivalent to the well-known equation for the thermionic emission current¹⁶ (here shown for electrons, an entirely similar expression holds for holes):

$$J_n = A^* T^2 \exp\left(-\frac{q\phi_{Bn}}{kT}\right) \exp\left(\frac{qV_{\text{applied}}}{kT}\right)$$

where A^* is the Richardson constant.

To fully model the current at a Schottky contact, the tunneling current through the Schottky barrier needs to be correctly simulated. This can be done in Sentaurus TCAD by using the nonlocal tunneling model at the interface between the metal and the semiconductor. To simulate the tunneling current in this work, a WKB-based model has been selected for the tunneling probability^{17,18}. Details of the model will not be presented here and can be found elsewhere^{7,19}.

The simple expression for the calculation of Schottky barrier presented above is valid only for an ideal system and cannot model alone the experimental values measured in fabricated devices. The value of the barrier heights of metal-semiconductor systems are, in general, determined by both the metal work function and the interface states¹⁷, which can depend very much on the fabrication process. Thus, the Schottky barrier of fabricated devices are usually extracted experimentally. One of the best methods is the activation-energy method. The thermionic emission current expression can be rewritten as:

$$\ln\left(\frac{I}{T^2}\right) = \ln(AA^*) - \frac{q(\phi_{Bn} - V_F)}{kT}$$

¹⁵ Sentaurus Device of Synopsys TCAD, User Guide, V-2023.12

¹⁶ S. M. Sze, Physics of Semiconductor Devices, New York: John Wiley & Sons, 2nd ed., 1981

¹⁷ K. Matsuzawa *et al.*, "A unified simulation of Schottky and ohmic contacts," in IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices, vol. 47, no. 1, pp. 103-108, Jan. 2000, doi: 10.1109/16.817574

¹⁸ C. Huang, *et al.*, "Two-dimensional numerical simulation of Schottky barrier MOSFET with channel length to 10 nm," IEEE Trans. Electron Devices, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 842-848, Apr. 1998

¹⁹ M. Jeong, *et al.*, "Comparison of Raised and Schottky Source/Drain MOSFETs Using a Novel Tunneling Contact Model," in IEDM Technical Digest, San Francisco, CA, USA, pp. 733-736, December 1998.

where A is the electrically active area of the metal-semiconductor interface and V_F is the forward bias applied voltage. Over a limited range of temperature around room temperature, the value of A^* and ϕ_{Bn} are temperature independent: from the slope of a plot of $\ln\left(\frac{I}{T^2}\right)$ versus $1/T$ it is possible to obtain the barrier height ϕ_{Bn} (whereas the ordinate intercept at $1/T = 0$ gives the product of the electrically active area A and the effective Richardson constant A^*). This method was developed for a Schottky diode, i.e. a structure in which one contact is a Schottky contact and the second contact is Ohmic. However, Schottky barrier can be extracted also from measurements of Schottky Barrier Field effect transistors (SBFETs), i.e. FET gated structure with two Schottky source and drain contacts. In this case, the activation-energy method should be used to compute an effective Schottky Barrier Height (eSBH) using the measured drain currents at different temperatures, fixing the gate and drain voltage. We have employed the activation-energy method to compute the effective Schottky Barrier Height (eSBH) from experimental data measured on SBFET fabricated by our collaborators in TU Wien, sketched

Figure VII – Structure of the fabricated and simulated SBFET.

Figure VIII - Richardson plot for the measured drain current at gate voltage of 0.5 V and drain voltage of 0.1 V.

in Fig. VII, also published in literature²⁰. In particular, we used measured drain currents at 295 K, 323 K, 348 K, 373 K, 398 K, fixing the gate and drain voltage. Fig. VIII reports an example of a Richardson plot for a gate voltage of 0.5 V and a drain voltage of 0.1. The eSBH was extracted as a function of drain and gate voltage, as shown in Fig. IX. The SBH of the single metal semiconductor junction, without effects from the FET gate, can be inferred by selecting the eSBH at small drain voltage and at a gate voltage close to the flat band voltage (equal to 0.5 V for the ideal gate stack in Fig. VII). Considering the results in Fig. IX and considering also previous extraction done in TU Wien on several similar devices, the SBH of the Al/p-Si system fabricated in TUWien is estimated to be in an interval between 0.5 and 0.6 eV. After extracting the value for the SBH, the structure in Fig. 7 has been simulated in Sentaurus Device to verify the simulation results and extract the parameters for the tunneling current model. In particular, the tunneling masses for electron and holes have been calibrated (staying within the range of values reported in literature^{21,22}). The simulated drain current – gate voltage and drain current – drain voltage curves, after calibration, are reported against experimental results in Fig. X and Fig. XI. The SBH used in simulation is 0.6 eV. The tunneling mass extracted were: $0.3m_0$ for electrons and $0.2 m_0$ for holes (within the range of values reported in literature^{23,24}). The simulation also includes interface fixed positive charges between the silicon layer and the top silicon oxide layer with a concentration of $5 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. With these parameters, the simulations exhibit a rather good agreement with experimental results.

Figure IX – Effective Schottky Barrier Height, extracted using the activation-energy method, as a function of gate voltage for different drain voltages (left) and as a function of drain voltage for a gate voltage of 0.5 V (right).

²⁰ L. Wind et al. “Monolithic and Single-Crystalline Aluminum–Silicon Heterostructures”, ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces 2022, 14, 22, 26238–26244, doi: 10.1021/acsami.2c04599

²¹ T. Baldauf *et al.*, “Tuning the tunneling probability by mechanical stress in Schottky barrier based reconfigurable nanowire transistors”, Solid-State Electronics 128 (2017) 148–154

²² J. Hu *et al.*, “Schottky Tunneling Effects in a Tunnel FET”, IEEE Transactions On Electron Devices, Vol. 64, No. 12, 2017

²³ T. Baldauf *et al.*, “Tuning the tunneling probability by mechanical stress in Schottky barrier based reconfigurable nanowire transistors”, Solid-State Electronics 128 (2017) 148–154

²⁴ J. Hu *et al.*, “Schottky Tunneling Effects in a Tunnel FET”, IEEE Transactions On Electron Devices, Vol. 64, No. 12, 2017

Figure X – Simulated SBFET drain current as a function of gate voltage (structure as in Fig. 7), in solid lines, compared to experimental data (symbols). The drain-source voltage is 1V.

Figure XI - Simulated SBFET drain current as a function of drain voltage (structure as in Fig. 7), in solid lines, compared to experimental data (symbols). The gate voltage is -3 V.

c. Simulation of Fe-SBFET

A total of 8 TCAD simulation setups have been developed, to simulate the two Fe-SBFETs design options in 2D and 3D and using either the Preisach-based model or the Landau-based model. First of all, the device structures and the corresponding meshes and electrodes were constructed. Fig. 2 reports the 8 devices structures used in the 8 TCAD setups. As explained in

the previous section, for a correct description of the ferroelectric layer, featuring multidomains, using the Landau-based model, the ferroelectric region needs to be divided in ferroelectric

Figure 2. Structures used in the TCAD simulations of the two design options of the Fe-SBFET (left: structures for simulations using Preisach-based model; right: Landau-based model).

Figure 3. Voltage applied to the program gates or front gate as a function of time for reset and write

boxes connected by non-ferroelectric spacers: each box represents a ferroelectric domain and has a slightly different polarization reversal characteristics compared to the other domains. In simulations, this was obtained by imposing different coercive fields in the boxes, in particular a Gaussian distribution of coercive fields. For this reason, the structures constructed for simulation are more complex than the structures used for simulation with the Preisach-based model, for which only a single ferroelectric region is needed. In the structures in Fig. 2 the metal regions of the source, drain and gate (program and back gates) are not present. The metal contacts are simulated as “electrodes”, shown in the figure in magenta, i.e., electrical boundary conditions: the metal

volume region is not needed, thus it is not present in the simulated structure. In fact, both Ohmic and Schottky contacts can be set within the “electrode” definition, together with the specification of the metal work function (or alternatively the Schottky barrier height). Materials and sizes of the simulated structures, whose results are reported in this deliverable, are summarized in Table I. Sentaurus TCAD, through the “workbench” program, offer the possibility to “parametrize” in the input scripts different quantities, such as dimensions of the different layers, material type, number of ferroelectric domains etc, so that they can be easily using the graphical interface, so that the design-space can be efficiently analyzed. Acceptor and donor interface traps at the ferroelectric/dielectric interface have been included in the simulation. A proper inclusion of interface traps is paramount to obtain realistic simulations. Several experimental and simulation studies^{25,26,27} of silicon based FeFETs have shown that the HZO-SiO₂ oxide stack features a large density of traps, leading to a trapped charge comparable to the polarization charge. Trapped charges stabilize the HZO polarization charge by reducing the otherwise very large depolarization field in the ferroelectric layer. Accurate calibration of interface traps for a HZO-SiO₂ stack has been performed in a previous work²⁸: traps parameters from this work have been used. In particular, simulations include donor and acceptor interfacial traps at the HZO-SiO₂ interface with a Gaussian energy distribution (for acceptors, the distribution is centered at 1.85 eV below the conduction band of HZO and for donors it is centered at 3.17 eV below conduction band of HZO). The traps exchange electrons and holes via a non-local tunneling mechanisms across the SiO₂, accounting for both elastic and multi-phonon assisted tunneling. The parameters are reported in Table II. Finally, regarding the semiconductor, the conventional drift-diffusion model was used. For generation–recombination processes, Shockley–Read–Hall (SRH) model was used. Fermi-Dirac statistics was selected.

In Fe-SBFETs, the tunnelling at the Schottky barrier is modulated by the polarization-induced band bending in the semiconductor layer. In an SBFET, especially with large SBH for both

²⁵ K. Toprasertpong *et al.*, 2019 IEEE IEDM, p. 23.7.1– 23.7.4, doi:10.1109/IEDM19573.2019.8993664

²⁶ S. Zhao, *et al.*, IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices, vol. 69, no. 3, pp. 1561–1567, 2022, doi:10.1109/TED.2021.3139285

²⁷ S. Deng, *et al.*, 2020 IEEE International Electron Devices Meeting (IEDM), 2020, pp. 4.4.1–4.4.4, doi:10.1109/IEDM13553.2020.9371999.

²⁸ D. Lizzit, *et al.*, IEEE TED, vol. 72, no.3, p. 1083 – 1090, 2025, doi: 10.1109/TED.2025.3526104

electrons and holes as in this case, the Schottky contact resistance has a large impact on the on-state current of the transistor and the drain current can be modulated by several order of magnitude. Preliminary simulations have been carried out to study the behavior of the Schottky junctions and the polarization-induced modulation of their barrier. Results of such preliminary simulations are reported in Appendix A.

Table I. Material and thicknesses of regions in simulated Fe-SBFETs.

	Material	Layer thickness
Ferroelectric (FE)	Hf _{0.5} Zr _{0.5} O ₂ (HZO) - ferroelectric orthorhombic phase	8.5 nm
Non-FE oxide	Hf _{0.5} Zr _{0.5} O ₂ (HZO) – non ferroelectric phase	8.5 nm
Interface oxide	SiO ₂	0.9 nm
Semiconductor	Silicon	20 nm
Back Oxide	SiO ₂	50 nm

Table II. Parameters used for interface traps at the HZO-SiO₂ interface.

	Acceptor-type traps	Donor-type traps
Center of Gaussian energy distribution	1.85 eV below the conduction band of HZO	3.17 eV below conduction band of HZO
Standard deviation of Gaussian energy distribution	0.04 eV	0.04 eV
Concentration	10 ¹⁴ cm ⁻²	10 ¹⁴ cm ⁻²
Electron/hole effective mass	0.8 m ₀	0.8 m ₀
Trap volume	10 ⁻¹² μm ³	10 ⁻¹² μm ³

Results of simulations of Fe-SBFETs are reported in the next section. Transient simulations have been performed in Sentaurus TCAD. The structure is biased by applying time-varying voltages at the electrodes. A work function of 4.5 eV is used for the program gates or front gate and back gate, whereas a Schottky barrier of 0.6 eV is chosen for the source and drain electrodes, as detailed above. The ferroelectric polarization is first set by applying a write voltage pulse, after a first reset pulse used to start from a known polarization state. The reset and write pulses are applied at the program gates or at the single gate electrode, depending on the type of structure under test. During the reset and write, the back gate, drain and source electrodes are kept at 0 V. After the write pulse, the drain current of the Fe-SBFET is read by applying a linear sweep at the gate voltage, or back gate voltage for the structures employing program gates and back gate. During the read operation, the drain-source voltage is kept at 0.5 V. In particular, the drain contact is biased at 0.25 V and the source contact is biased at -0.25 V, following the bias scheme used in this work²⁹.

²⁹ D. Nazzari D, et al., ACS Appl Mater Interfaces. 2025 Feb 19;17(7):10784-10791, doi: 10.1021/acsami.4c16400

3. Simulation results

This section will present the simulation results of the different TCAD setups regarding the structure in Fig. 1a, i.e the one with the ferroelectric only on top of the Schottky junctions, with a back gate to perform the read operation. The structure is firstly biased using the bias scheme in Fig. 3 to set the polarization state. The voltage pulses are applied at the program gates and the drain, source and back electrodes are kept at 0 V. Then, a linear voltage sweep to the back gate is applied while applying

Figure 4. Average ferroelectric polarization as a function of time during reset and write operations (2D setup, Preisach-based model).

0.25 V to the drain and -0.25 V to the source, as explained in the previous section (the program gates are at 0 V). First of all, the results obtained using the 2D TCAD setup with Preisach-based model are reported. The average polarization as a function of time during the reset and the set pulse is reported in Fig. 4 (the polarization is aligned along the x-direction in Fig. 2). Increasing the pulse height from 0.5 V to 5 V, it is possible to obtain a gradual modulation of the polarization in a wide range of values. The polarization in Fig. 4 is the average polarization in the whole ferroelectric HZO layer. Fig. 5.a shows that, as expected, the polarization in the HZO region above the source Schottky junction is the same as the polarization in the HZO region above the drain Schottky junction. Fig. 5.b reports the charge trapped at the interface between HZO and SiO₂, calculated considering the charge of both electrons and holes trapped at the interface. The traps are charged during the gate voltage pulses. The positive trapped charge, given by the occupation of the donor-type traps, helps to stabilize the negative polarization when the program gate voltage goes back to zero after the reset pulse. The negative trapped charge, given by the occupation of the acceptor-type traps, stabilizes the positive polarization after the write pulse. The trapped charge partially compensates the polarization and the resulting attenuated polarization modulates the Schottky junctions at source and drain, in particular the barrier width and so the tunneling through the barrier, thus modulating the drain current in the Fe-SBFET. The drain current as a function of the back gate voltage is plotted in Fig. 6 for different write voltage pulse heights. For write voltages that result in a negative polarization, the Fe-SBFET behaves as a p-type FET and the drain current is high for negative back gate voltages. The polarization in fact induces a band bending in the semiconductor region close to the Schottky contacts that favors the tunneling of holes and blocks electrons. For increasing write voltages, the polarization increases and eventually becomes positive. Plots of the band diagram highlighting polarization-induced band bending are reported in Appendix A. When the polarization is almost 0, namely for a write voltage of

0.25 V to the drain and -0.25 V to the source, as explained in the previous section (the program gates are at 0 V).

First of all, the results obtained using the 2D TCAD setup with Preisach-based model are reported. The average polarization as a function of time during the reset and the set pulse is reported in Fig. 4 (the polarization is aligned along the x-direction in Fig. 2). Increasing the pulse height from 0.5 V to 5 V, it is possible to obtain a gradual modulation of the polarization in a wide range of values. The polarization in Fig. 4 is the average

Figure 5. a) Ferroelectric polarization of the HZO regions on top of the source and drain Schottky contact as a function of time during reset and write operations (2D setup, Preisach-based model); b) Charge in the traps at the interface between HZO and SiO₂.

1.5 V, the Fe-SBFET has always a low current as the Schottky barrier is not modulated, and so neither the tunneling of holes nor the tunneling of electrons can be enhanced. For positive

polarization values, the Fe-SBFET behaves as an n-type FET and the drain current increases increasing the write voltage and so the positive polarization value.

Fig. 7 reports the comparison of the results obtained with the 2D and 3D TCAD setup, using the Preisach-based model. As it can be seen in Fig. 7.a, the average polarization in the HZO layer obtained performing 2D simulations is the same as the one obtained with 3D simulations (width of 20 nm). As a consequence, also the drain current versus back gate voltage curves are very similar in the 2D and 3D case. This outcome was expected and it is related to the use of the Preisach-based model. In fact, the latter model corresponds to a macroscopic hysteretic system composed by a superposition of simple hysteresis units, so it already considers an averaged value of the polarization over several ferroelectric domains. In the Preisach-based model, the polarization depends on the electric field and on the polarization history of the material. Thus, since the 3D structure is homogeneous along the z-axis, the same polarization as in the 2D case is found for the same applied voltages. However, the simulation time of the 3D case is much longer, about 20 to 50 times longer than the 2D case.

Figure 6. Drain current of the Fe-SBFET as a function of the back gate voltage for different write voltage pulse heights. The read operation is performed with a back gate voltage sweep, with program gates at 0 V, drain at 0.25 V and source at -0.25 V, after the end of the write operation (2D setup, Preisach-based model).

Figure 7. Comparison between 2D and 3D setup using the Preisach-based model: a) average polarization as a function of time during reset and set time; b) read operation: drain current as a function of the back gate voltage.

The results obtained with the 2D TCAD setup employing the Landau-based model are reported in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. The structure is simulated in two fashions, featuring either ferroelectric domains with a boundary between two domains placed in correspondence of the Schottky

junction (structure a) or with a single ferroelectric domain placed on top of the Schottky junction (structure b). The domains have a lateral size of 7 to 10 nm, in the range of experimentally reported values³⁰. For this reason, in a 2D structure only very few domains can be inserted in the ferroelectric region (3 or 4 in each ferroelectric region, see Fig. 8). The result is a very limited multidomain gradual switching of the polarization that can have only few levels, due to the insufficient number of domains. This type of simulated structure is thus not representative of the fabricated devices, where a higher number of domains are usually found due to the extension of the device in the third dimension, which is considered homogeneous in 2D simulations. Nevertheless, structures featuring very few ferroelectric domains have been experimentally observed in highly scaled FeFETs³¹. In addition, in the Fe-SBFET with the ferroelectric layer only on top of the Schottky junctions, the ferroelectric region that can modulate the Schottky barrier is only the part of the ferroelectric close to the junction lying on top of the semiconductor. In structure a, the drain current is thus affected only by two domains while in structure b four domains can affect the read-out current (see FE domains in red in Fig. 8, top panels). As it can be seen in Fig. 8, for structure a we thus have four possible configurations corresponding to the two relevant domains having both a positive polarization, both a negative polarization, or finally having opposite polarizations. In simulations, by changing the pulse height from 0.5 V to 2 V, three different configurations have been obtained, as it can be seen in Fig. 8, middle panel. Consequently, only three different drain current versus back gate voltage characteristics have been found, reported in Fig. 9.a, even though five different pulse heights have been tested. For pulse heights of 0.5 V and 0.75 V, the relevant domains have negative polarization in both cases, and so the same p-type drain current versus back gate voltage is found. The same applies for pulse heights of 1.5 V and 2 V, but with positive polarization and an n-type read-out characteristic. For the pulse height of 1 V, the negative polarization at source favors the tunneling of holes and the positive polarization at drain favors the tunneling of electrons, hence, the Fe-SBFET has a high value of current for both positive and negative back gate voltage due to this ambipolar behavior. In structure b we would have more configurations given the four domains involved. However, in the read-out operation (see Fig. 9.b) we see that we could obtain only two types of drain current versus back gate voltage characteristics: n-type or always off. The n-type is obtained when all the four domains are positive. In all the other cases there is one of the two domains on the source side having negative polarization, thus blocking the tunneling of electrons, and one of the two domains on the drain side with positive polarization, thus blocking the tunneling of holes. Different domains with different distribution of coercive voltages could result in different polarization patterns and the p-type of ambipolar characteristics could be obtained. However, also in this case very few levels in the drain current can be obtained, as the two adjacent domains either have the same polarization, so the same effect, or opposite polarization, where one effect contrast the other.

For these reasons, the 2D simulations employing the Landau-based model have limited application for modeling of fabricated Fe-SBFETs and will not be further used.

³⁰ H. Mulaosmanovic, J. Ocker, S. Müller, U. Schroeder, J. Müller, P. Polakowski *et al.*, “Switching Kinetics in Nanoscale Hafnium Oxide Based Ferroelectric Field-Effect Transistors”, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, vol. 9, no. 4, 2017.

³¹ H. Mulaosmanovic, E. T. Breyer, S. Dünkel, S. Beyer, T. Mikolajick, and S. Slesazek, “Ferroelectric field-effect transistors based on HfO₂: a review,” *Nanotechnology*, vol. 32, no. 50, p. 502002, 2021.

Figure 8. Polarization after write pulses with different heights in two structures with different positioning of the FE domains with respect to the Schottky junctions (2D setup, Landau-based model).

Figure 9. Drain current as a function of back gate voltage read out after the end of the write pulse at different voltage heights: a) for the structure a in Fig. 8 and b) for the structure b in Fig. 8 (2D setup, Landau-based model).

The Landau-based model can be more effectively implemented in 3D simulations, so to obtain a high enough number of ferroelectric domains.

Simulations using the 3D TCAD setup employing the Landau-based model have been carried out using the same bias scheme discussed before. Fig. 10 reports the polarization obtained in the HZO layer after the write pulse, using different pulse heights. As done for the 2D structure, also in the 3D case the simulations are performed for two slightly different structures featuring a different alignment between the Schottky junction and the ferroelectric domains boundaries.

Figure 10. Polarization of the ferroelectric domains in the HZO layer after write pulses at different heights (3D setup, Landau-based model). The structure a and the structure b differ in the alignment between the Schottky junction and the ferroelectric domains boundaries.

It can be seen how the gradual switching, and so a multilevel operation, can be obtained by dividing the ferroelectric layer in several independent homogeneous domains with a Gaussian distribution of coercive fields. By increasing the voltage of the write pulses, the number of

Figure 11. Average polarization in the HZO region during reset and write pulses at different heights (3D setup, Landau-based model) in structure a and structure b (see Fig. 10).

Figure 12. Drain current versus back gate voltage: read operation after write pulses at different heights for structure a and b (3D setup, Landau-based model).

domains that switches from a negative polarization (obtained after the reset pulse) to a positive polarization increases. Even though the total number of domains is higher with respect to the

Figure 13. Current density for a back gate voltage of -5 V (3D setup, Landau-based model).

Figure 14. Current density for a back gate voltage of 5 V (3D setup, Landau-based model).

2D case, also in this case only the few domains close to the Schottky junction and lying on top of the semiconductor affect the Schottky barrier and so the current in the Fe-SBFET. For the pulse heights considered in our analysis, two different configurations of the relevant domains are found, as for 2 V and 3 V we have the same configuration and, thus, the same drain current versus back gate voltage curve, as it can be seen in Fig. 12. Structure a and structure b give slightly different results. The 3D plots of the current density in the structures for a back gate voltage of -5 V are reported in Fig. 13. Structure b has a higher current for a pulse height of 1 V because there are more domains around the Schottky junction with negative polarization, in particular there are domains with negative polarization in the whole ferroelectric width thus enhancing everywhere the tunneling of holes. Both structure a and b for pulse heights of 2 V and 3 V have full lines of domains with positive polarization at source thus blocking the holes. For a back gate voltage of 5 V, the drain current for 2 V and 3 V write pulses is almost the same in structure a and b (the current density is plotted in Fig. 14), given by the comparable polarization patterns.

A higher number of possible configurations of polarization can be obtained by increasing the number of domains along the Schottky junctions, namely increasing the width of the structure. However, the increase of the number of domains leads to convergence issues and it is impossible to obtain results. In fact, the overlap between the Schottky junction and the ferroelectric region degrades the convergence and results can be obtained only for specific values of interface traps and pulse lengths, even for a small number of domains. In particular, it has been seen that simulations with a high number of domains correctly converges when the Schottky junction is placed far from the ferroelectric, whereas they fail to converge when the Schottky junction is placed below the ferroelectric, as in a Fe-SBFET. Even when the simulations of the Fe-SBFET converges (as for the examples in Fig. 10-14), the simulation time is very long, making it difficult to simulate a large design-space to perform a study on

optimization strategies. Fig. 15.a and Fig. 15.b reports the comparison of the results obtained with the 3D TCAD setup employing the Landau-based model and the results obtained with the 2D TCAD setup employing the Preisach-based model. Even though the results of the two setups

Figure 15. a) Comparison of the average polarization in the HZO region during reset and write pulses at different heights for the 3D setup with the Landau-based model (structure a and structure b) and for the 2D setup with the Preisach-based model; b) comparison of drain current versus back gate voltage after write pulses at different heights for the 3D setup with the Landau-based model (structure a and structure b) and for the 2D setup with the Preisach-based model.

do not perfectly match, if we consider the low number of domains used for the 3D case, the results obtained are rather good.

Simulations of FeFETs employing the division of the ferroelectric layer in many domains with homogeneous polarization, instead as simulating the full layer using a Preisach-based approach, are particularly useful when studying the percolation path problem³². In a conventional FeFET with the ferroelectric layer on top of the channel, the current does not depend only on the polarization state but also by the spatial distribution of the ferroelectric domains with positive/negative polarization. As it can be seen in Fig. 16, the domains with positive polarization can create high conductance paths (with a high electron density) from source to drain, resulting in a high value of the FeFET drain current. If the domains with positive polarization are spatially arranged in such a way that a conductive path between source and

Figure 16. Simulation results of a conventional FeFET (from [6]): a) ferroelectric polarization; b) electron density obtained for the maximum reading gate voltage (1.2 V); c) sketch of the percolation paths from source to drain.

drain is not formed, then the FeFET drain current has a low value. These two situations could happen at the same write condition and average polarization value in the HZO layer and negatively impact the multilevel operation of the FeFET. The percolation path problem thus cannot be correctly model employing a single ferroelectric region modeled with a macroscopic Preisach-based. However, it is only relevant in structures where the ferroelectric layer is placed on top of the FET channel. The Fe-SBFET structure having the ferroelectric regions only on top of the Schottky junctions are not affected by this problem. In fact, the single domain on top of the Schottky junction only affects the part of the barrier that has below: the full Schottky junction would behave as many junctions in parallel, each differently modulated by the corresponding ferroelectric domain. For this reason, a complex model employing the ferroelectric divided in several domains is not strictly needed and, for such a structure, the 2D TCAD setup with the Preisach-based model will be preferred. The percolation path would nevertheless affect the other Fe-SBFET design featuring the ferroelectric on top of both the Schottky junctions and the channel. For this other type of structure, when studying the percolation path problem, a 3D TCAD setup with multiple domains have to be used.

³² D. Lizzit, T. Bernardi and D. Esseni, “Multi-level Operation of FeFETs Memristors: the Crucial Role of Three Dimensional Effects”, ESSDERC 2022 - IEEE European Solid-State Device Research Conference (ESSDERC)

4. Calibration to experimental measurements

In this section, the developed TCAD setup will be used to study and simulate the Fe-SBFET devices fabricated in TUWien³³. The sketch and SEM micrographs of the device-under-test are shown in Fig. 17. The silicon layer (20 nm) sits on top of a thick silicon oxide layer (100 nm). The top gate is composed of an HZO layer (8.5 nm) on top of a thin (0.9 nm) silicon oxide interface layer. The semiconductor region is contacted by aluminum source and drain contacts, forming a Schottky contact of about 0.6 eV (as extracted before). Two TiN program gates are deposited on top of the Schottky junctions. The semiconductor channel length is about 3.5 μm and the width is 500 nm. Simulations of this structure are carried out with the 2D TCAD setup employing the Preisach-based model. As shown in the previous section, the 2D Preisach-based TCAD setup is the best choice for the type (a) structure in Fig. 1 (i.e., with ferroelectric layer only on top of the Schottky junctions), for which the percolation path problem does not need to be simulated. In this case, we do not need to simulate individual domains, so the Preisach-based

Figure 17. a) Sketch of the structure of the Fe-SBFET fabricated in TUWien. The ferroelectric orthorhombic phase of the HZO in contact with the TiN program gates (PG) is shown in colours. b) Scanning electron - microscope image of the fabricated device. Labels identify the source (S), drain (D) and program gate (PG) contacts. The inset shows an optical microscope image of the same device. c) Pulsing and transfer (read-out) biasing scheme used in the measurements and related device configuration.

³³ D. Nazzari, L. Wind, M. Sistani, D. Mayr, K. Kim and W. M. Weber, "Ferroelectrically-enhanced Schottky barrier transistors for Logic-in-Memory applications", preprint on arXiv:2404.19535, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2404.19535>

model, which is faster and less prone to convergence issues, can be used instead of the Landau-based model. Given the use of the Preisach-based model and the symmetry of the structure, a 2D setup can be used, resulting in faster simulations without impacting the accuracy of the results (see results presented in the previous section). The Preisach-based model of the ferroelectric layer polarization versus voltage curve has been already calibrated on experimental data of ferroelectric capacitor employing the same HZO layer as in the fabricated Fe-SBFET (see section 2.a). Here, the measured transfer characteristic, obtained after the write pulse as shown in Fig. 17.c, is compared to the simulation results using the same bias scheme. In order to obtain a good fit to the experimental data, the traps present at the HZO/SiO₂ (top oxide) interface and at the Si/SiO₂ (back oxide) interface had to be calibrated. Moreover, fixed charge trapped in the non-ferroelectric HZO, placed on top of the silicon channel, due to oxygen-related defects, has also been included³⁴. Figure 18 reports a sketch of the simulated device, showing graphically where the traps have been included. The calibrated I_d-V_g curves (using the back gate as shown in Fig. 17.c) are compared to the measured data in Fig. 19. The curves are obtained, both in experiments and simulations, after a reset pulse at -3 V (duration of pulse: 0.5 ms) and a set pulse at 1.5 V and 4.5 V (duration of pulse: 0.5 ms). The concentration and type of traps used in simulations are reported in Table III. The on-current is different in the n-type and p-type characteristics: the n-type characteristics shows a lower on-current due to the higher compensation of the polarization given by the acceptor-type traps at the HZO-SiO₂ interface. In simulations, a higher concentration of acceptor-type traps with respect to donor-type traps have been selected in order to obtain this asymmetry in on-currents. The measured transfer curves have a subthreshold swing (SS) of 1.25 V/dec for the n-type characteristics and of 4.32 V/dec for the p-type characteristics. These very high SS values stem from the presence of interface traps at the Si/SiO₂ (back oxide) interface, whose effect is emphasized by the use of a very thick

Figure 18. Sketch of the simulated structure. Traps have been included at the at the HZO/SiO₂ (top oxide) interface, at the Si/SiO₂ (back oxide) interface and in the bulk of the non-ferroelectric HZO. The concentration and type of traps are reported in Table III.

³⁴ J.L. Lyons et al., “The role of oxygen-related defects and hydrogen impurities in HfO₂ and ZrO₂”, *Microelectronic Engineering*, 88, 1452–1456, (2011)

oxide below the gate (the back gate is used for the read-out). Fig. 20 shows the simulated characteristics without any traps at the Si/SiO₂ (back oxide) interface (and without fixed charge in the non-ferroelectric HZO), compared to the simulated characteristics in which acceptor-type traps (below silicon conduction band) and donor-type traps (above valence band) have been inserted at the Si/SiO₂ (back oxide) interface. More details on the parameters of these traps are in Table III. In Fig. 19, it can be seen that the measured I_d-V_g characteristics are shifted towards positive back gate voltage values (quite high positive value), which is not found in the simulated characteristics in Fig. 20. The shift is due to the presence of negative fixed charge at the Si/SiO₂ (back oxide) interface and in the bulk of non-ferroelectric HZO. In order to correctly simulate the shift found in experimental data, firstly negative fixed charge has been inserted at the Si/SiO₂ (back oxide) interface. Fig. 21.a shows the comparison of the simulated curves with and without fixed charges (-10^{12} cm⁻² at the Si/back oxide interface). It was not possible to obtain the measured shift only including this type of fixed charges, because the shift of the n-type characteristic is lower with respect to the p-type characteristic, whereas the fixed charge at the Si/back oxide interface gives a solid consistent shift for both the characteristics. On the contrary, fixed charge in the non-ferroelectric HZO results in a larger shift for the p-type characteristic with respect to the n-type characteristic, as shown in Fig. 21.b, where the fixed charge in the HZO was set to $-1.2 \cdot 10^{18}$ cm⁻³. By properly calibrating these two types of fixed charges, it was possible to obtain a good fit to the experimental data, as shown in Fig. 21.b, and before in Fig. 19. These results have been also published in literature³⁵.

Figure 19. Calibrated I_d-V_g curves (solid line) and experimental data (symbols). The read-out is performed after a reset pulse at -3 V (duration of pulse: 0.5 ms) and a set pulse at 1.5 V and 4.5 V (duration of pulse: 0.5 ms). The concentration and type of traps used in simulations are reported in Table III.

³⁵ D. Nazzari, C. Rossi *et al.*, "Non-Volatile Reconfigurable Transistor via Ferroelectric Modulation: Fabrication Strategy and TCAD Simulations," 2025 International Semiconductor Conference (CAS), Sinaia, Romania, 2025, pp. 3-11, doi: 10.1109/CAS66707.2025.11222346

Figure 20. Simulated characteristics without any traps at the Si/back oxide interface and without fixed charge in the non-ferroelectric HZO (dashed line) and with acceptor-type traps and donor-type traps at the Si/back oxide interface (solid line). The parameters of traps used in simulations are reported in Table III.

Figure 21. Simulated characteristics with acceptor-type traps and donor-type traps at the Si/back oxide interface: a) with and without fixed charges at the Si/back oxide interface (-10^{12} cm^{-2}) and b) with fixed charges at the Si/back oxide interface and with and without fixed charges in the bulk of the non-ferroelectric HZO ($-1.2 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). The parameters of traps used in simulations are reported in Table III.

Table III. Calibrated parameters of traps used to fit experimental transfer characteristics.

<i>Traps at the HZO-SiO₂ interface</i>	Acceptor-type traps	Donor-type traps
Center of Gaussian energy distribution	1.85 eV below the conduction band of HZO	3.17 eV below conduction band of HZO
Standard deviation of Gaussian energy distribution	0.04 eV	0.04 eV
Concentration	$8 \cdot 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	10^{14} cm^{-2}

<i>Traps at the Si/back oxide interface</i>	Acceptor-type traps	Donor-type traps
Type of energy distribution	uniform	uniform
Energy range	0-0.5 eV below the conduction band of silicon	0-0.6 eV above the valence band of silicon
Concentration	$2.25 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$	$7.2 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$
Fixed charge	-10^{12} cm^{-2}	

<i>Traps in the bulk of the non-ferroelectric HZO</i>	
Fixed charge	$-1.2 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$

A. Appendix

Preliminary simulations have been carried out to study the behavior of the Schottky junctions and the polarization-induced modulation of their barrier. The simulated structure is shown in Fig. A1. For this study, the Preisach-based model has been selected for the ferroelectric layer due to computational reasons. A concentration of $1 \cdot 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ has been used for acceptors and holes at HZO/SiO₂ interface. Such traps exchange electrons and holes via a non-local tunneling mechanisms across the SiO₂, accounting for both elastic and multi-phonon assisted tunneling (SiO₂ tunneling electron/hole effective mass of $0.8 m_0$ and a trap volume of $10^{-12} \mu\text{m}^3$). Simulations have been performed by applying voltage pulses at the program gate (the two gates on top of the Schottky junctions are short circuited together), more specifically a reset pulse at a fixed voltage ($\pm 5 \text{ V}$) and a set pulse at different heights. The source, drain and back gate contact are at 0 V , if not specified differently.

Figure A1 – Simulated Fe-SBFET structure.

Figure A2 – Simulated polarization in the HZO ferroelectric layer (averaged) as a function of time, for different set pulse voltages, using the pulsing scheme described in Fig. 14. The reset pulse height is -5 V .

Simulated results of the average polarization in the HZO ferroelectric region as a function of time are reported in Fig. A2, using a negative reset pulse (- 5V) and for different set pulse height. It can be seen how partial polarization switching is obtained for pulses at different voltages. It has to be noted that the polarization is not constant in the entire ferroelectric region, as shown in Fig. A3: the ferroelectric layer sandwiched between two metal contacts has a higher polarization with respect to the region placed on top of the semiconductor, where part of the electrostatic potential drops in the semiconductor. Fig. A4 compares the average polarization in the ferroelectric layer to the average polarization in the ferroelectric region on top of the metal source contact and the average polarization of the region on the semiconductor.

Fig. A5(a.b.c.) shows the simulated conduction and valence band along the cutline C1, in the silicon layer just below the top gate, shown in Fig. A5.a. The band diagrams are plotted for the structure after the reset pulse at - 5 V (at gate voltage of 0 V) and after the set pulse at 5 V (at gate voltage of 0 V). It can be seen that, after the reset pulse inducing a negative polarization, the Schottky barrier has a shape which favors tunneling of holes and blocks tunneling of electrons: namely the Fe-SBFET works as a p-type FET. After the set pulse the polarization is positive, instead, and the band bending is such that tunneling of electrons is allowed: namely

Figure A3 – Results of the simulated polarization, showing the higher value of the stabilized polarization in the HZO region above the metal contact. Simulations refer to the structure at a gate voltage equal to 0 V (as for drain, source, back gate voltage), after the reset pulse and a set pulse of 3 V (left) and 5 V (right).

Figure A4 - Simulated polarization in different region of the HZO ferroelectric layer (above the metal contact, above the semiconductor region, averaged in the full ferroelectric HZO region) as a function of time, for different set pulse voltages, using the pulsing scheme described in Fig. 14. The reset pulse height is - 5V.

Figure A5.a – Conduction band E_c and valence band E_v (b) along the cutline C1 (a) in the silicon layer. Magenta and blue refer to the structure after the reset pulse (gate voltage of 0 V), whereas red and green refers to the structure after reset and set pulse at 5 V (gate voltage of 0 V). Drain-source voltage is set to 0 V and back gate voltage is set to 0 V.

the Fe-SBFET works as an n-type FET. Fig. A6 shows the band diagram after set pulses at different heights (always computed at gate voltage of 0 V): the width of the Schottky barrier becomes smaller with increasing pulse height, thus tunneling of electrons becomes more effective. The resulting drain current, for a gate voltage of 0 V, back gate voltage of 4 V and drain-source voltage of 0.5 V, as a function of set pulse voltage is plotted in Fig. A7. It can be

seen that, by varying the set pulse between 1 V and 5 V, it is possible to obtain a variation of 6 order of magnitude in the drain current, which is consistent with experimental results^{33,35}.

Figure A5.b – Conduction band E_c and valence band E_v along the outline C1 (Fig. A5.a) in the silicon layer after reset (a) and set (b). Drain-source voltage is set to 0.5 V and back gate voltage is set to 0 V.

a)

b)

Figure A5.c – Conduction band E_c and valence band E_v along the cutline C1 (Fig. A5.a) in the silicon layer after reset (a) and set (b). Drain-source voltage is set to 0.5 V and back gate voltage is set to 5 V.

Figure A6 - Conduction band E_c and valence band E_v along the cutline C1 (Fig. A5.a) in the silicon layer (gate voltage of 0 V) for different set pulse heights, i.e. different polarization states in the ferroelectric HZO layer.

Figure A7 – Simulated drain current (computed at gate voltage = 0V, back gate voltage = 4 V, drain-source voltage = 0.5 V) as a function of set pulse voltage (applied after reset pulse at -5 V).